

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON THE DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF STEPPED AND PLY-DROP TAPERED SKIN DOUBLER REPAIRS UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental study on the damage tolerance of stepped and ply-drop tapered skin doubler repairs when subjected to fatigue loading. Graphite/epoxy ply was used for the doubler and parent adherend with a stacking sequence of (45/0/0/-45/90)_{3S}. Each specimen was 360 mm long and 20 mm wide. The bondline damage at the tip of the doubler repair was simulated by a Teflon tape. Various flaw sizes were selected by changing the flaw length and flaw width. A total of thirty specimens were tested consisting of fifteen specimens with stepped doubler repair and the other fifteen specimens with ply-drop doubler repair. A constant amplitude fatigue loading was applied to all specimens. The crack propagation was recorded and the fatigue life was reported. The effect of the initial flaw on the damage tolerance of the two types of skin doubler repairs was discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

There has been an increase in the demand of replacing mechanically fastened metallic patches with bonded composite patch repair to increase the service life in aircraft operations [1, 2]. However, no credit is currently given to the patch system when applied to primary structure [2]. Also the bondline integrity cannot be ensured with a lack of damage tolerance information [3, 4].

The work in the literature on the damage tolerance of bonded repair was conducted mainly on aluminium adherends [1, 2, 5-7]. For example, the skin doubler specimens were proposed in [2] for characterising the threshold for damage growth in the safe-life zone, which was used in the design of F111 repair in [8]. Charlkley et al. [5] presented an experimental study on the skin doubler specimens prepared by bonding composite skin doubler repair on aluminium adherend. However, no initial damage was introduced in the bondline (thus lack of damage tolerance information). Poole [6] reported an experimental programme on the damage tolerance of skin doubler repairs to the cracked aluminium adherend under fatigue loading. The experimental results indicated that no debond growth was detected for initial flaw when subjected to constant fatigue loading. Similar results were reported by Roach [7], where it was found the size of the initial flaw remained almost unchanged until the fracture of the aluminium plate under fatigue loading.

This paper presents an experimental study on the damage tolerance of tapered skin doubler repairs bonded on graphite/epoxy laminate adherend when subjected to fatigue loading. Two types of tapered skin doubler repair were selected, named stepped doubler and ply-drop doubler. Various initial flaws were introduced in the doubler repair bondline, by changing the flaw length and flaw width. Constant

amplitude fatigue loading was applied to all doubler repaired specimens. The crack propagation was monitored and measured by a microscope during the fatigue loading. Fatigue life was determined when the crack reached a length of 100 mm. The failure modes, fatigue life and the crack propagation against the number of fatigue cycles were reported and compared. Finally, the effect of initial bondline flaw on the damage tolerance of these two types of skin doubler repair was discussed and concluded.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Materials

Thirty plies of IM7/977-3 were used to prepare the laminate adherend and doubler repair with a stacking sequence of $(45/0/0/-45/90)_{3S}$. Stepped doubler and ply-drop doubler were manufactured by staggering equal-size plies with a 3 mm offset to achieve the stepped taper at one end, and the ply-drop taper at the other, as shown in Figure 1. The parent laminate was manufactured in the same process as the skin doubler panel but without tapered ends. The top and bottom surfaces of the parent laminate were made smooth with a caul plate, whilst the top surface of the doubler panel was prepared with a silicon intensifier.

Figure 1: Schematic of tapered panel manufacture.

FM300-2K was used as adhesive and cured under full vacuum condition in an oven at 125 °C for 120 mins. The detailed configurations of stepped and ply-drop doublers are shown in Figure 2, with the red line representing the adhesive bondline.

Figure 2: (a) Stepped doubler; (b) Ply-drop doubler (bondline in red).

2.2 Skin Doubler Repaired Specimens with Initial Flaws

The skin doubler repaired specimen was 360 mm long and 20 mm wide. The initial flaw was located at the tip of the doubler repair and was prepared using Teflon sheets. Three lengths were selected for the initial flaw, which were 5 mm, 10 mm and 20 mm. Two widths were used at 5 mm and 20 mm simulating a partial width flaw and a full width flaw, respectively. Control specimen without an initial flaw was also prepared for comparison purpose. The detailed dimensions of the skin doubler

repaired specimen with embedded initial flaw are shown in Figure 3. A spacer (70 mm long, 20 mm wide and 3.9 mm thick) was bonded on the other end of the specimen for clamping purpose when applying the fatigue loading.

Figure 3: Detailed dimensions of the skin doubler repaired specimen, and location and dimensions of the full width flaw and partial width flaw (unit in mm).

All prepared specimens are listed in Table 1. The first letter in the specimen label represents the doubler type (i.e. 'S' for stepped doubler and 'P' for ply-drop doubler), followed by the flaw size (Length×Width), and the last number indicates the ID of repeating specimen.

Table 1: Specimens and main experimental results.

Specimen	Flaw length (mm)	Flaw width (mm)	Fatigue life (cycles)
S-Control-1	0	0	27,487
S-Control-2	0	0	24,798
S-Control-3	0	0	28,073
S-5×5-1	5	5	>180,000
S-5×5-2	5	5	>180,000
S-5×5-3	5	5	>180,000
S-5×20-1	5	20	>180,000
S-5×20-2	5	20	>180,000
S-5×20-3	5	20	>180,000
S-10×20-1	10	20	1,143
S-10×20-2	10	20	1,068
S-10×20-3	10	20	1,516
S-20×20-1	20	20	391
S-20×20-2	20	20	320
S-20×20-3	20	20	200
P-Control-1	0	0	>180,000
P-Control-2	0	0	>180,000
P-Control-3	0	0	>180,000
P-5×5-1	5	5	>180,000
P-5×5-2	5	5	>180,000
P-5×5-3	5	5	>180,000
P-5×20-1	5	20	>180,000
P-5×20-2	5	20	>180,000
P-5×20-3	5	20	>180,000
P-10×20-1	10	20	2,465
P-10×20-2	10	20	2,380
P-10×20-3	10	20	2,070
P-20×20-1	20	20	1,044
P-20×20-2	20	20	783
P-20×20-3	20	20	1,313

2.3 Experimental Setup and Instrumentations of Fatigue Tests

The fatigue tests were conducted on a fatigue machine of Instron 1342 with a loading capacity of 100 kN. The fatigue loading ranged from 1.87 kN to 18.7 kN with a frequency of 3 Hz. A microscope AD7013MZT from Dino-Lite Digital Microscope, was used to monitor the crack propagation process at an resolution of 2592×1944 pixels and a magnification of 50 times. Six marks were made on the observation surface of the specimen which was painted in white using a correction pen. The marks had a spacing of 20 mm, with the first mark at the doubler tip (see Figure 3). The fatigue life was defined as the number of cycles when the crack reached the final mark (100 mm from doubler tip). All specimens were loaded to failure otherwise continued to 180,000 cycles. The experimental setup of the fatigue tests is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Experimental set up of fatigue testing on the skin doubler repaired specimens.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Failure Modes

The typical failure modes of stepped doubler repair and ply-drop doubler repair are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. Ply-drop doubler repaired specimens failed when the flaw was no less than 10 mm long. For shorter initial flaw, ply-drop doubler repaired specimens did not fail even after 180,000 cycles. Similarly, stepped doubler repaired specimens failed when the initial flaw size was longer than 10 mm. However, the stepped doubler with an initial flaw of 5 mm long survived after 180,000 cycles, whilst specimens without an initial flaw failed.

Figure 5: Failure modes of specimens with stepped doubler repair with a flaw size of (a) without initial flaw; (b) 5×5 mm²; (c) 5×20 mm²; (d) 10×20 mm²; (e) 20×20 mm².

Figure 6: Failure modes of specimens with ply-drop doubler repair with a flaw size of (a) without initial flaw; (b) 5×5 mm²; (c) 5×20 mm²; (d) 10×20 mm²; (e) 20×20 mm².

3.2 Crack Propagation and Fatigue Life

The crack propagation was plotted against the number of cycles in Figure 7. The left side of Figure 7 shows the crack propagation curves of failed specimens with an initial flaw size of 10×20 mm² or 20×20 mm², and the right side presents the crack propagation curves of stepped doubler specimens without an initial flaw. The crack length in Figure 7 was measured from the doubler tip.

Figure 7: Crack propagation of failed stepped doubler (solid symbols) and ply-drop doubler (hollow symbols) repaired specimens.

As can be seen in Figure 7, the crack firstly grew slowly before it reached a length of about 30 mm, after which the crack became unstable and grew rapidly up to 90 mm. Considering S-20×20 failed rapidly as soon as the fatigue load was applied, it is recommended that the bondline flaw of stepped doubler repair should not exceed 20 mm length which may lead to unstable crack growth under fatigue loading.

The fatigue life was defined as the number of cycles when the crack reached 100 mm length. The fatigue life of each specimen is listed in Table 1. The fatigue life is denoted as '>180,000' cycles if not failed. It is evident in Table 1 that, the ply-drop doubler repair performed better than the stepped doubler repair in terms of damage tolerance under fatigue loading. For example, P-Control survived after 180,000 cycles, comparing to S-Control which failed at an average fatigue life of 26,786 cycles. Both stepped and ply-drop doubler repaired specimens survived 180,000 cycles when the imbedded flaw length was 5 mm. When the flaw was 10 mm long, P-10×20 achieved an average fatigue life of 2,305 cycles, which is almost two times of the average fatigue life (1242.3 cycles) of S-10×20. When the embedded flaw size increased to 20 mm long, the fatigue life of the P-20×20 (1046.7 cycles) was two times higher than that of S-20×20 (303.7 cycles).

One unexpected observation is that the stepped doubler repair without an initial flaw (S-Control) failed at 26,786 cycles, whilst it did not fail with an initial flaw of 5 mm long. The authors hypothesize that the introduction of an embedded flaw of 5 mm length suppressed the crack initiation tendency on the tapered doubler and shifted the crack initiation to the tip of the initial flaw. Detailed microscope investigations on the crack initiation and propagation pattern are currently being conducted to support the hypothesis.

4 CONCLUSIONS

An experimental program on the damage tolerance behaviour of stepped doubler repair and ply-drop doubler repair of graphite/epoxy laminate under fatigue loading was presented. Various initial bondline flaws were introduced by changing the flaw length and width. Constant amplitude fatigue loading was applied to all doubler repaired specimens. The fatigue life of specimen was recorded and the crack growth against the number of cycles was presented. Based on the current experimental results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Ply-drop doubler repair performs better than stepped doubler repair in terms of damage tolerance under fatigue loading. When there was no initial bondline flaw, the ply-drop doubler repair survived 180,000 cycles fatigue loading, while the stepped doubler counterpart failed at an average fatigue life of 26,786 cycles. When the initial flaw was 10 mm long, the ply-drop doubler repair achieved an average fatigue life of 2,305 cycles, which is almost twice of the average fatigue life the stepped doubler repair. At an initial flaw size of 20 mm long, the ply-drop doubler repair had an average life of 1046.7 cycles, which is about three times of the average fatigue life of stepped doubler repair.
- Under fatigue loading, the crack firstly grew slowly before reaching 30 mm length, after which the crack became unstable and grew quickly until approaching 90 mm.
- The stepped doubler is not a desirable configuration for skin doubler repair applications, because it failed under fatigue loading even without an initial bondline flaw. Detailed microscope investigation on the crack initiation and propagation pattern of stepped doubler repair without initial flaw is under going to explain the unexpected experimental observations.
- The results in this paper suggest that when considering doubler tip flaws, an inspection technology should be adopted capable of detecting damage down to a threshold size of 5 mm.

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